

Strengthening Cybersecurity Certifications through Robust Chain of Custody Practices

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Abstract - In the nowadays, when cyber-security certification plays very important role and build the trust between customers and vendors/manufacturers, ensuring the integrity and trustworthiness of whole certification process, is paramount. This paper explores possibilities for integration of chain of custody concept within cybersecurity certification frameworks to fortify assurance mechanisms and process. Drawing upon digital forensic methodologies, the research proposes a novel approach to enhance the reliability and credibility of cybersecurity certifications process and possible used “evidences”. By leveraging chain of custody concept through blockchain technology, the paper propose documentation and tracking of the certification evidence throughout the entire certification lifecycle. This approach come from digital forensic and digital investigation, and perspective not only strengthens the verifiability of certification claims but also contributes to a more robust and transparent cybersecurity ecosystem. Potential benefits and challenges of incorporating and integrating chain of custody practice into cybersecurity certification processes also will be considered. Ultimately, this research aims to pave the way for a more secure and trustworthy cyber landscape by promoting the adoption of rigorous forensic practices in cyber security certification assurance.

Keywords— *Digital forensic, chain of custody, cybersecurity certification, blockchain technology, DEMF, evidence ensuring.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Today's digital landscape is almost fully interconnected, and the importance of cybersecurity certification cannot be overstated. With cyber threats, which evolve in sophistication and frequency [1], ensuring the integrity and trustworthiness of the certification process of products, processes, and services is supreme. However, traditional certification frameworks often face challenges in providing robust assurance mechanisms that effectively mitigate risks and establish confidence among stakeholders. In any compliance check process, audit process, certification process is challenged to ensure integrity and reliability of the evidence which are common uploaded, sent, distributed, or stored on some way with the aim to “prove something”.

Those evidence are mostly used to “prove” some compliance, fulfilment of some conditions, or simple to be just

evidence. Those are nearly always in digital form and because of that are very vulnerable. So, it could be said that digital evidence are not only related to the computer crime and digital investigation process, this concept is used very often today in the context of “*properties of undifferentiated copy*” originality, as well as in the process when something need to be proved [2].

In response to these challenges, this paper advocates for the possible integration and use of chain of custody concept within cybersecurity certification processes. Drawing upon methodologies from the field of digital forensics, this approach aims to enhance the reliability, transparency, and accountability of cybersecurity certifications.

The concept of chain of custody is commonly utilized in legal and forensic contexts to document the chronological history of evidence, as well as ensure that access to the evidence is fully controlled and audited [3], and this could offer a promising framework for strengthening certification assurance mechanisms. The concept is indeed well-established in digital forensics, but its direct application to cybersecurity certification is less commonly discussed in literature although the principles of maintaining integrity and authenticity through a documented chain of custody are relevant to the certification process. The chain of custody in the context of cybersecurity certification would involve ensuring that all steps, from evidence collection to the issuance of the certification, are thoroughly documented and securely handled to maintain trustworthiness.

By systematically documenting the custody, control, and integrity of evidence throughout the certification lifecycle, chain of custody concept can provide verifiable assurance regarding the authenticity and reliability of certified products, processes, and services. This forensic perspective not only bolsters the credibility of certification claims but also facilitates more effective incident response and forensic investigation in the event of security breaches or incidents. By promoting the adoption of rigorous digital forensic practices in certification assurance, this research seeks to contribute to a more secure and trustworthy cyber landscape, thereby safeguarding critical assets and enhancing resilience against emerging cyber threats.

II. CYBERSECURITY CERTIFICATION PROCESS

Cybersecurity certification is the process which requires the formal evaluation of the products, services and/or processes, by an independent and accredited body against defined set of criteria or standard and at the end issuing a certificate indicating this conformance [4].

This process plays a crucial role in the terms of increasing trust in security of using such a products, services and processes and strengthen confidence of it. The main part of the certification process is conformity assessment, defined in ISO 17000 [5], as process of demonstrating that some specific requirements are fulfilled. Conformity assessment can include few activities such as: testing, inspection, validation, verification, etc.

The high-level certification process is shown in Figure 1:

Fig. 1. Certification process flow

As shown in Figure 1, certification process is initiated by owner of the product (HW or SW), and depending of the nature of the product and of the security requirements (level of security), it can be self-assessed (for basic assurance level), or for higher assurance level (substantial/high) assessed by official auditor (assessor) using set of security testing tools. This official auditor is always conformity assessment body which is accredited for such an activity. At the end of certification process certificate of compliance is issued to the product owner if the requirements are fulfilled.

III. CHAIN OF CUSTODY FRAMEWORK

As already stated, the concept of chain of custody is very well-established in digital forensics and is one of the main parts of this process, but its direct application to cybersecurity certification is less commonly known. However, the principles of maintaining integrity and authenticity through a documented chain of custody are relevant to the certification process. The chain of custody in the context of cybersecurity certification would involve ensuring that all steps, from evidence collection to the issuance of the certification, are thoroughly documented and securely handled to maintain trustworthiness.

There are few proposed frameworks for chain of custody [6]. These frameworks typically emphasize the importance of documentation, secure storage, and controlled access to digital evidence throughout its lifecycle. They also highlight the need for clear procedures and training to ensure that all individuals involved in the handling of digital evidence understand and adhere to chain of custody protocols.

A several EU Projects also dealt with the chain of custody topics [7], [8], [9]. Blockchain technology solution proposed in these projects utilizes a fully-fledged solution that offers privacy and confidentiality, identity management, efficiency and modular design. Blockchain technology employs an architecture that will help network participants to share information over a fair, secure, scalable, and transparent channel.

IV. METHODOLOGY

Importance of using chain of custody concept from traditional digital forensic process in cyber security certification process is on the first place to ensure that digital evidence (digital files) used in the certification process remains untampered and authentic from the point of collection to the final certification. Second thing is with what approach we will maintains transparency and trust in the certification process, especially critical in sectors where high security is mandatory, i.e. NIS2 directive scope [10].

Challenges in "traditional" cybersecurity certification processes are commonly related to the lack of transparency, difficulty in verifying certification claims, and the dynamic nature of cyber threats that necessitate continuous reassessment of certification requirements.

Challenges in proposed novel approach will be:

- Adapting digital forensic chain of custody practices to fit the certification workflow,
- Ensuring that every step in the certification process, including data collection, analysis, storage, archiving, etc. adheres to strict documentation and security protocols,
- Integrating chain of custody protocols into automated certification systems without compromising efficiency and the costs.

Used methodology in this paper is multi-faced and is based on best practice and relevant standard, as well as on authors experience from past EU projects. First will be conducted all proposed and existing framework which are related to the chain of custody concept and digital forensic. After that, second step is to identify best practice and processes in cyber-

security certification process and for those purpose will be used ENISA recommendation [4], and EUCC as well [11].

The aim is to understand current practices and pinpoint areas where chain of custody best practice can be enhanced. Finally, at the end, future research will be based on developing a proposed framework tailored to cybersecurity certification, detailing specific documentation, security controls, audit trails, and training requirements. In later phase, framework will be evaluated in one conformity assessment body through one use-case.

Chain of custody concept refers to the accurate auditing control of original evidence material that could potentially be used for legal purposes [12]. The purpose of testimony concerning chain of custody is to prove that evidence has not been altered or changed through all phases, and must include documentation on how evidence is gathered, how was transported, analysed and presented.

Knowing the current location of original evidence is not enough for court (in legal cases), there must be accurate logs tracking evidence material at all times. Access to the evidence must be controlled and audited [13]. That means actually, that we need to know answer on every possible question, where is, who, when, why, how accessed to the evidence, as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Used concept for establishing and ensuring chain of custody [2]

In EU funded project Puzzle [8], in terms of chain of custody, smart contracts are introduced. Smart contracts are simply programs stored on a blockchain that run when predetermined conditions are met. These self-executing contracts with the terms of the agreement between transacting entities have found numerous applications in the modern world and thrive anywhere a system with centralized authority has failed or is problematic. Considering that smart contracts dictate how and when the transacting peers interact, must be carefully designed to cover all necessary cases, but also provide an Application Programming Interface (API) to be upgraded if necessary.

The decentralized framework that Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) are offering has allowed to proceed and

create trust between interacting entities with the use of blockchain technology and the tools it offers. PUZZLE project [8] embraces this mature and tested technology to insert trust, confidentiality, and security in its systems.

PUZZLE project [8], needs the individual organizations to interact with each other, in order to have a very secure network of communication and data storage. To this end, this solution is selected to utilize a fully-fledged solution that offers:

- Privacy and confidentiality,
- Identity management,
- Efficiency,
- Modular design.

The technology that offers all the above is the Hyperledger Fabric (HLF) [15]. HLF was established under the Linux Foundation, which itself has a long and very successful history of nurturing open-source projects under open governance that grow strong, sustaining communities and thriving ecosystems. Fabric has a highly modular and configurable architecture, enabling innovation, versatility, and optimization for a broad range of industry use cases. This allows to set up a network that will support the PUZZLE project services [8], experiment on it, and customizing every parameter for the needs of project.

A key concept that Fabric offers is the use of smart contracts. The blockchain concept that is used by Fabric is a combination of a data bank that holds facts about the current historical state of a set of objects, and the smart contracts that define the executable logic that generates new facts that are added to the ledger.

In the Fabric ecosystem, the terms “*smart contract*” and “*chaincode*” are often used interchangeably, but for overall approach and for a better understanding of the overall technical architecture of proposed solution, it is needed to clarify the precise meaning of each definition. The “*chaincode*” is a mechanism of Fabric that groups related “*smart contract*” for deployment, while each smart contract is like a function that is part of the chaincode. In other words, the smart contracts are packaged into a chaincode which is then deployed to the blockchain network. The chaincode governs how smart contracts are packaged and how they will be used later to interact with the network.

We also need to briefly explain one core component of the Fabric network. The ledger in Fabric consists of the world state and the blockchain. The world state is a distinct database that holds the current values of a set of ledger states-assets, while the blockchain integrates a transaction log that records all the changes that have resulted in the current world state. As in any other blockchain architecture, transactions are collected inside blocks that append to the blockchain, providing a clear understanding of the history of changes that have resulted in the current world state.

As shown in Figure 4, a ledger (L) comprises a blockchain (B) and a world state (W), where B determines W. The Fabric architecture maintains multiple copies of a ledger in the network, which are distributed among peers and are kept consistent with every other copy through a consensus process, realizing the Distributed Ledger Technology.

Fig. 3. Ledger components in Fabric ecosystem

Proposed solution presents practical example of projects that have successfully implemented chain of custody protocols in their cybersecurity assurance processes.

In this way, the final solution of the secure mechanisms are designed, deployed, and used for realizing the secure, fair, and scalable data exchange between different organisations. To this end the basis of setup is the Hyperledger Fabric (HLF), and all the services that are integrated and allowed the system components to interact and exchange Collective Threat Information (CTI) with each other over a blockchain network that is set up.

Furthermore, a set of smart contracts that could convey information about certification processes are tested. These sets of smart contracts will not only cover all actions that needed by the system of certification, but also could provide a basis for more improvements by arranging a canvas of endpoints and methods that make certification system scalable, interoperable, legal compliant and it was carefully integrated to also preserve fairness throughout every process of the system, and to the blockchain core network.

V. INTEGRATION OF CHAIN OF CUSTODY PRACTICES IN CYBERSECURITY CERTIFICATION PROCESS

This section explains possible framework for integrating chain of custody protocols into cybersecurity certification processes. It discusses the various stages of the certification lifecycle, including assessment, audit, and accreditation, and identifies opportunities for incorporating chain of custody procedures to enhance assurance mechanisms.

The main parts of the proposed architecture will be “Chain of custody management layer”, as well as “Chain of custody enforcement layer”. The concept will also be a part of the “Reporting and certification layer”. Cryptographic techniques will be used for hashing and digital signature to ensure the integrity from the point of data collection and systems like blockchain technology solution [8], [9], will be used to ensure that data cannot be altered.

Documentation system will log every action taken on data, including timestamps and audit trail will record that trace data handling and processing activities. In the certification process layer will be possibilities to validate the findings and ensure compliance with chain of custody (is the chain of custody established and unchanged or not). Any change in chain of custody will be reported in alert and notification component. A comprehensive report will be created at the end where could

be seen who is, when, where, why and how accessed to the evidence in the certification process.

Fig. 4. Architecture for applying chain of custody concept

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section outlines the potential benefits of integrating chain of custody concept into cybersecurity certification processes, as well as proposed for future research direction. So, the systematic documentation and tracking of evidence can improve the verifiability, reliability, and credibility of certification claims, thereby enhancing trust among stakeholders.

The model of the chain of evidence affects both the certification process and the possibility of repeatability of the certification process, which influences the creation of stronger trust in the certification process and enables, in case of need, every step of the certification process. In addition, the model can also serve as a security mechanism in case of challenging the certification process as well as in the context of proving each individual step, which makes the whole process not only more transparent but also easily provable. The chain of proof model represents the future in many security systems and applications because it provides a very solid and robust mechanism for ensuring integrity and provability in a simple way.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

In conclusion, the integration of chain of custody protocols presents a promising approach to addressing the challenges and limitations of traditional cybersecurity certification processes. By leveraging digital forensic methodologies to systematically document and track the custody, control, and integrity of evidence throughout the certification lifecycle, organizations can enhance the

reliability, transparency, and accountability of certification assurance mechanisms.

Throughout this paper, authors have explored the potential benefits of integrating chain of custody best practices into cybersecurity certification processes, including improved verifiability of certification claims, enhanced trust among stakeholders, and more effective incident response and forensic investigation capabilities. Case studies and practical implementations will be demonstrated in the future to show the feasibility and effectiveness of this approach in real-world scenarios, despite the challenges and considerations involved.

Moving forward, it is essential for organizations to continue exploring and adopting innovative approaches to certification assurance, particularly in the face of evolving cyber threats and regulatory requirements. Future research efforts should focus on addressing the challenges identified in this paper, such as scalability, interoperability, and legal compliance, while also exploring opportunities for further refinement and optimization of chain of custody integration frameworks.

In conclusion, by embracing rigorous forensic practices in certification assurance processes, organizations can contribute to a more secure and trustworthy cyber landscape, thereby safeguarding critical assets and enhancing resilience against emerging cyber threats. The integration of chain of custody concept represents a significant step towards achieving this goal and ensuring the integrity of cybersecurity certifications in an increasingly interconnected world.

Finally, at the end, future research will be based on developing a proposed framework tailored to cybersecurity certification, detailing specific documentation, security controls, audit trails, and training requirements and in later phase, framework will be evaluated in one conformity assessment body.

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